

Numerical Approximation of Atangana-Baleanu Caputo Fractional Derivative and Its Application to Fractional Order Subdiffusion Bioheat Equation

Jagdish Sonawane[#], Bhausaheb Sontakke^{*}, Kalyanrao Takale[#]

[#]GES R. H. Sapat College of Engineering, Management Studies and Research, Nashik-422005. (M.S.) India.

^{*}Pratishthan College, Paithan. Dist. Aurangabad. 431107. (M.S.) India.

[#]RNC Arts, JDB Commerce and NSC Science College, Nashik-Road, Nashik, India.

Abstract- To address the limitations of the classical fractional derivative, which uses a local and singular kernel, Caputo and Fabrizio recently introduced a new fractional derivative with a non-local and non-singular exponential kernel. Atangana and Baleanu further generalized this derivative using the Mittag-Leffler function. In this paper, we apply the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo fractional derivative to develop a fractional-order finite difference scheme for solving the fractional-order subdiffusion bioheat equation. The stability and convergence of this method are demonstrated both numerically and graphically. Python code is provided to obtain numerical and graphical solutions for the fractional-order subdiffusion bioheat equation.

Keywords and phrases- Fractional Differential Equations, Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo Fractional Derivatives, Subdiffusion Bioheat Equation, Mittag-Leffler Function, Python Programming, etc.

I. Introduction

Fractional calculus is a branch of mathematics with wide-ranging applications[12] in biology, economics, physics, engineering, chemistry, and more. Recently, researchers have increasingly used fractional operators in place of ordinary operators to achieve more accurate models of physical phenomena[6]. Mathematicians such as Riemann-Liouville, Grunwald-Letnikov, Caputo, Riesz, and Hadamard have developed various classical definitions of fractional derivatives[6,16]. However, using these definitions to model non-local dynamical systems is limited due to the local and singular nature of the kernel[20]. To address this, Caputo and Fabrizio introduced a new definition of the fractional derivative featuring a non-singular and non-local exponential kernel, which was later generalized by Atangana and Baleanu using the Mittag-Leffler function as the kernel[6, 10]. Numerous researchers have since applied this definition in various physical models[9, 21, 22, 23].

These definitions are beneficial for solving nonlinear systems, for which numerical approximations are essential due to their complexity. Recently, researchers have developed various numerical methods for solving nonlinear systems[14, 25, 26, 27, 28, 32]. Numerical approximations for the Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivative were introduced by Atangana et al.[3] and Yadav et al.[31]. In this paper, we employ this approximation with the finite difference method, applying the numerical approximation of the Atangana-Baleanu Caputo fractional derivative[23] to the fractional-order bioheat equation developed by Takale et al.[28]. In 1948, Harry H. Pennes was the first to develop a mathematical model for temperature distribution in the resting human forearm[15]. This model, known as the bioheat transfer equation, is expressed as follows:

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T(x,t)}{\partial t} = k \frac{\partial^2 T(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + W_b C_b (T_a - T) + Q_r, \quad x \in [0, L], t \in [0, T]$$

where T represents temperature, t is time, ρ is density, C is specific heat, x is distance, k is thermal conductivity, T_a is the arterial temperature, W_b is the blood perfusion rate, Q_r is the constant volumetric heat, and C_b is the specific heat of blood.

Many researchers have developed modified versions of Pennes' bioheat models[4, 7,8,15,18] and introduced various solution techniques[11, 30]. Damor (2013), Ezzat (2014), and Ferras (2015) developed fractional bioheat models using the Caputo fractional derivative[5, 8, 9]. Asjad and Zhang recently applied the Atangana-Baleanu and Caputo-Fabrizio fractional derivatives to various fractional bioheat models[2]. In this paper, we discuss the fractional bioheat model developed by Takale et al.[28], is given by

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha Z^*}{\partial t^\alpha} + \frac{W_b C_b}{\rho C} Z^* - \frac{1}{\rho C} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(g(x) \frac{\partial Z^*}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{Q_r}{\rho C}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq L, 0 \leq t \leq T$$

where $Z^* = T - T_a$, $k = g(x)$, and $\frac{\partial^\alpha Z^*}{\partial t^\alpha}$ denotes the Caputo fractional derivative with $0 < \alpha \leq 1$.

Letting $Z = Z^* - \frac{Q_r}{W_b C_b}$, $a = \frac{W_b C_b}{\rho C}$, $b = \frac{1}{\rho C} > 0$,

we obtain
$$\frac{\partial^\alpha Z}{\partial t^\alpha} + aZ - b \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(g(x) \frac{\partial Z}{\partial x} \right) = 0,$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $0 \leq x \leq L$, and $0 \leq t \leq T$.

Initial Condition: $Z(x, 0) = 0$, for all x

Boundary Conditions: $Z(0, t) = Z_0$, $Z(L, t) = 0$, for all t

The time fractional derivative introduces subdiffusion or superdiffusion without altering the properties of material density and specific heat. Subdiffusion is a process characterized by time memory. The subdiffusion equation involves a fractional derivative of order α , which serves as the subdiffusion parameter. It is important to note that when $\alpha = 1$, normal diffusion occurs, and when $0 < \alpha < 1$, subdiffusion is observed. In this work, we modify the fractional bioheat equation (1.1)-(1.3) by replacing the

Caputo fractional derivative of order α with the Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivative in the context of subdiffusion, i.e., $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Thus, the fractional-order subdiffusion bioheat equation is given by:

$$\frac{{}^{ABC}\partial^\alpha Z}{\partial t^\alpha} + aZ - b \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(g(x) \frac{\partial Z}{\partial x} \right) = 0,$$

where $0 < \alpha < 1$ and $x \in [0, L]$, $t \in [0, T]$.

Initial Condition: $Z(x, 0) = 0$, for all x

Boundary Conditions: $Z(0, t) = Z_0$, $Z(L, t) = 0$, for all t

The paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we discuss some fundamental definitions of fractional derivatives. Section 3 covers the discretization of the Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivative and its application in the development of a finite difference scheme for solving the fractional-order subdiffusion bioheat equation (1.4). The stability and convergence of the developed finite difference scheme are addressed in Section 4. In Section 5, we present the approximate solution of the subdiffusion bioheat transfer equation using a Python code developed by us. Finally, Section 6 provides the conclusions.

II. Definitions of Fractional Calculus

Definition 2.1 Riemann-Liouville Fractional integral:[16]

$${}_0J_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-u)^{\alpha-1} f(u) du,$$

where $f(t) \in C[0,1]$ and $\alpha \in (-\infty, \infty)$.

Definition 2.2 Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivative:[16]

$${}_0D_t^\alpha f(t) = D_1 {}_0I_t^{1-\alpha} f(t) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-u)^{-\alpha} f(u) du \right),$$

where $f(t) \in C[0,1]$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Definition 2.3 M.Caputo Fractional Derivative:[16]

$${}_0D_t^\alpha f(t) = {}_0I_t^{1-\alpha} D_1 f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-u)^{-\alpha} f'(u) du,$$

where $f(t) \in C[0,1]$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Let $M(\alpha)$ be a normalization function that satisfies $M(0) = M(1) = 1$.

Definition 2.4 Caputo-Fabrizio Fractional Derivative:[13]

$${}_0D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{M(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \int_0^t \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(t-u)\right) f'(u) du,$$

where $f(t) \in H^1(0,1)$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Definition 2.5 Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo Fractional Derivative:[3]

$${}_0D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{M(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \int_0^t E_\alpha\left(-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(t-u)\right) f'(u) du,$$

where $f(t) \in H^1(0,1)$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, and $E_\alpha(z)$ is the Mittag-Leffler function defined as

$$E_\alpha(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)}.$$

III. Finite difference scheme

To develop the Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme [20] for the subdiffusion bioheat transfer equation (1.4)-(1.6), we define $x_i = i\Delta x$, where $i = 0, 1, \dots, M$, and $t_n = n\Delta t$, where $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$. Here, $\Delta x = \frac{L}{M}$ and $\Delta t = \frac{T}{N}$. Let the exact solution of the subdiffusion bioheat transfer equation (1.4) at the mesh point (x_i, t_n) be $Z(x_i, t_n)$, where $i = 0, 1, \dots, M$ and $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$. Additionally, let Z_i^n represent the numerical approximation at the point (x_i, t_n) . Note that Δx is the spatial step size and Δt is the time step size.

The Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo type time fractional derivative is discretized [3] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{{}^{ABC}\partial^\alpha Z}{\partial t^\alpha} \right) &= \frac{M(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \int_0^{t_{n+1}} E_\alpha\left(-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(t_{n+1}-u)\right) \frac{\partial Z(x, u)}{\partial u} du \\ &= \frac{M(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^n \left(\frac{Z_i^{n+1} - Z_i^n}{\Delta t} \right) E_\alpha\left(-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(t_{n+1}-u)\right) du + R_{n+1} \\ \left(\frac{{}^{ABC}\partial^\alpha Z}{\partial t^\alpha} \right)_i^n &= \frac{M(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \left(\frac{Z_i^{n+1} - Z_i^n}{d_0} \right) + \frac{M(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{Z_i^{n-j+1} - Z_i^{n-j}}{d_j} \right) + R_{n+1} \end{aligned}$$

Where $d_j = ((j+1)E_{\alpha,2}(\eta_{j+1}) - jE_{\alpha,2}(\eta_j))$ and $\eta_j = -\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} [(j\Delta t)^\alpha]$

Here, the remainder R_{n+1} is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{n+1} &= \frac{M(\alpha)}{(1-\alpha)} \frac{(\Delta t)^2}{2} \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial t^2} \left((n-j+1)E_{\alpha,2}(\eta_{n-j+1}) - (n-j)E_{\alpha,2}(\eta_{n-j}) \right) \\ &\leq \frac{M(\alpha)}{(1-\alpha)} \frac{(\Delta t)^2}{2} \left(\max_{0 < t < t_n} \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial t^2} \right) C_1 \end{aligned}$$

where C_1 is a constant.

We now discretize the spatial derivative in equation (1.4) using the Crank-Nicolson method as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(g(x) \frac{\partial Z}{\partial x} \right)_i^n = \frac{1}{2(\Delta x)^2} [g_i(Z_{i-1}^{n+1} - 2Z_i^{n+1} + Z_{i+1}^{n+1}) + (2g_i - g_{i+1})(Z_{i-1}^n - 2Z_i^n + Z_{i+1}^n)]$$

where $g(x_i) = g_i$.

We can now discretize the fractional-order subdiffusion bioheat equation (1.4) using equations (3.1) and (3.3) as follows:

Lemma 4.4 Let $\lambda_i(B)$ and $\lambda_i(F)$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$, represent the eigenvalues of matrices B and F , respectively. Then, the following conditions hold: (i) $|\lambda_i(B)| \leq 1$ and $|\lambda_i(F)| \leq 1$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$.

(ii) $\|B_2\|_2 \leq 1$ and $\|F_2\|_2 \leq 1$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$.

Theorem 4.1 The solution to the fractional order Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme [19] (3.5)-(3.8) for the fractional order subdiffusion bioheat equation (1.4)-(1.6) is unconditionally stable.

Proof. We will demonstrate that $\|Z^n\|_2 \leq K \|Z_0\|_2$, where K is a positive constant independent of x and t .

For $n = 1$, we have

$$Z^1 = A^{-1}BZ^0 + A^{-1}C$$

Thus,

$$\|Z^1\|_2 \leq \|A^{-1}\|_2 \|B\|_2 \|Z^0\|_2 + \|A^{-1}\|_2 \|C\|_2 = K \|Z^0\|_2$$

Therefore, for $n = 1$, the result holds true.

Now, assume the result holds for $n \leq m$, i.e. $\|Z^m\|_2 \leq K \|Z^0\|_2$

For $n = m + 1$, we consider

$$Z^{m+1} = A^{-1}FZ^m + A^{-1}\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} (d_j - d_{j+1})Z^{m-j} + A^{-1}d_m Z^0 + A^{-1}C$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \|Z^{m+1}\|_2 &\leq \|Z^m\|_2 + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} (d_j - d_{j+1}) \|Z^{m-j}\|_2 + d_m \|Z^0\|_2 + \|C\|_2 \\ &\leq K(1 + d_1 + (1 - K_2)d_m) \|Z^0\|_2 + K_3 \\ &= K \|Z^0\|_2 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by induction, for all n , we have

$$\|Z^n\|_2 \leq K \|Z^0\|_2$$

where K is a positive constant independent of x and t . This confirms that the scheme is unconditionally stable. This completes the proof.

2. Convergence

Consider the region $\Omega: [0, L] \times [0, T]$. The exact solution of the fractional-order subdiffusion bioheat equation (1.4)-(1.6) at the time level t_n is represented by the vector of size $M + 1$ as follows:

$$\bar{Z}^n = (\bar{Z}(x_0, t_n), \bar{Z}(x_1, t_n), \bar{Z}(x_2, t_n), \dots, \bar{Z}(x_M, t_n))^T$$

Consider the truncation error as the vector $\tau^n = (\tau_1^n, \tau_2^n, \tau_3^n, \dots, \tau_M^n)^T$ at the time level t_n . Since Z_n is the exact solution to the equation (1.4)-(1.6), we have the following:

For $n = 0$:

$$AZ^1 = BZ^0 + C + \tau^1 \quad (4.4)$$

For $n \geq 1$:

$$AZ^{n+1} = FZ^n + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (d_j - d_{j+1})Z^{n-j} + d_n Z^0 + C + \tau^{n+1} \quad (4.5)$$

Lemma 4.5 The coefficients d_j , where $j = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$, satisfy the following conditions:

- (i) $d_j > 0$
- (ii) $d_j > d_{j+1}$ and $d_j \rightarrow 0$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$

Theorem 4.2 The fractional order Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme [19] (3.5)- (3.8) for fractional order subdiffusion bioheat equation (1.4)-(1.6) is unconditionally convergent.

Proof. Let the error vector $E^n = \bar{Z}^n - Z^n = (e_1^n, e_2^n, e_3^n, \dots, e_M^n)^T$ in solution at the time level t_n . Furthermore, assume that $|e_l^n| = \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |e_i^n| = \|E^n\|_\infty$ and $|\tau_l^n| = \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^n|$, $l = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Using equation (3.5), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} |e_1^1| &= |-\mu_1 g_i e_{i-1}^1 + (1 + 2\mu_1 g_i) e_{i^1} - \mu_1 g_i e_{i+1}^1| \\ &\leq (2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_1 g_{i+1}) |e_{i-1}^0| + (1 - 2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_2) |e_i^0| + \mu_1 g_{i+1} |e_{i+1}^0| + |\tau_i^1| \\ &\leq (2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_1 g_{i+1} + 1 - 2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_2 + \mu_1 g_{i+1}) \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |e_i^0| + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^1| \\ &\leq \|E_0\|_\infty + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^1| \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we obtain:

$$\|E^1\|_\infty \leq \|E^0\|_\infty + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^1|$$

From equation (3.6), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} |e_l^{m+1}| &= |-\mu_1 g_i e_{i-1}^{m+1} + (1 + 2\mu_1 g_i) e_i^{m+1} - \mu_1 g_i e_{i+1}^{m+1}| \\ &\leq (2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_1 g_{i+1}) |e_{i-1}^m| + (1 - 2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_2 - d_1) |e_i^m| + \mu_1 g_{i+1} |e_{i+1}^m| \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} (d_j - d_{j+1}) |e_i^{m-j}| + d_m |e_i^0| + |\tau_l^{m+1}| \\ &\leq (2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_1 g_{i+1} + 1 - 2\mu_1 g_i - \mu_2 - d_1 + \mu_1 g_{i+1}) |e_i^m| \\ &\quad + ((d_1 - d_2) + (d_2 - d_3) + \dots + (d_{m-1} - d_m)) |e_i^m| + d_m |e_i^0| + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^{m+1}| \\ &= \|E^m\|_\infty + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^{m+1}| \end{aligned}$$

This holds for every m , thus we have: $\|E^{m+1}\|_\infty \leq \|E^m\|_\infty + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^{m+1}|$

By induction, it follows that:

$$\| E^{n+1} \|_{\infty} \leq \| E^n \|_{\infty} + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^{n+1}|$$

Since $\| E^0 \|_{\infty} = 0$, we conclude that $\| E^n \|_{\infty} = 0$. Therefore, we have:

$$\| E^n \|_{\infty} \leq \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^{n+1}|$$

Since

$$\max_{1 \leq i \leq M} |\tau_i^{n+1}| \rightarrow 0$$

as $(\Delta x, \Delta t) \rightarrow (0,0)$, this implies that $\| E^n \|_{\infty} \rightarrow 0$ uniformly on Ω as $(\Delta x, \Delta t) \rightarrow (0,0)$. Hence, it is shown that for any x and t , the vector Z^n converges to \bar{Z}^n as $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, the proof is complete.

V Test Problem

We developed Python code to numerically solve the time fractional subdiffusion bioheat equation using the Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme of fractional order, as outlined in equations (3.5)-(3.8). In our test problem, we use the following parametric values, which are the same as those provided in [20]: $\rho = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $C = 4200 \text{ J/kg}\hat{\text{A}}^{\circ}\text{C}$, $W_b = 0.5 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $C_b = 4200 \text{ J/kg}\hat{\text{A}}^{\circ}\text{C}$, $L = 0.02416 \text{ m}$, and $T = 150 \text{ s}$. The initial temperature is set to $Z_0 = 120^{\circ}\text{C}$. We choose the function $g(x) = 0.7(1 + 3x)$ for x , with $\Delta x = 0.001208 \text{ m}$ and $\Delta t = 0.15 \text{ s}$. We have drwan some graphs by using above code as follow:

Figure 1: Comparison of temperature profiles along x direction at $t = 150\text{s}$. and $\alpha = 0.95$

Figure 2: Comparison of temperature profiles along x direction at $t = 150\text{s}$. and $\alpha = 0.9$

Figure 3: Comparison of temperature profiles along x direction at $t = 150s.$ and $\alpha = 0.85$

Figure 4: :Temperature elevations in skin at $x = 0:002416m$ and $\alpha = 0.95$

Figure 5: :Temperature elevations in skin at $x = 0:002416m$ and $\alpha = 0.9$

Figure 6: Temperature elevations in skin at $x = 0:002416m$ and $\alpha = 0.85$

We observe that the temperature profile at $t = 150$ s, obtained using the ABC method, is clearer than that obtained using the Caputo method. Additionally, the temperature increase from a specific point on the skin is faster with the ABC method compared to the Caputo method.

VI. Conclusions

We have successfully developed a fractional-order Crank-Nicolson scheme for the fractional-order subdiffusion bioheat transfer equation using the ABC time fractional derivative. The unconditional stability and convergence of the scheme have been proven. We obtained numerical solutions to the time fractional subdiffusion bioheat transfer equation, which are presented graphically using a Python code. From the graphical results, we observe that the ABC time fractional derivative is more effective for the subdiffusion bioheat transfer model compared to the Caputo time fractional derivative, as the ABC derivative provides a more detailed temperature profile.

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